

THE PRINCIPLES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF FIRSTAID, THE STRATEGY OF PROTECTING MOTHER AND CHILD

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ABSTRACT

Seventeen abused women in the public child welfare system were interviewed in-depth on the effects of domestic violence on their children and their protective and supportive strategies. They established cohesive ways to safeguard their children physically, but they also spoke about psychologically nurturing young children. Mothers reported practical approaches to promote their children's psychological resilience. It comes to domestic violence, concepts like protective strategies and mothering spring to mind.

Method & Materials

Participants

Applicants were 17 maltreated moms from lower to middle classes with minor children from a medium-sized midwestern city. CPS officers invited all victims of domestic violence with children aged 1 to 5. Because the impacts of domestic violence vary depending on the child's age, we selected to focus on the most devastating outcomes in this study. CPS caseworkers contacted mothers to ask permission to contact them for an interview. 44% of eligible mothers took part. Mothers received \$ 2.00 for their participation.

Six of the mothers were black, one white. Mothers ranged in age from 19 to 42. The average number of school years was 12, with a range of 1 to 16. A total of eight moms reported severe psychological issues, including stress-related and response sadness. At the time of the interview, 13 women had left their abusers. Eleven of the

women had adopted children, and six of them were kind to them while being supervised by CPS. The average mother had three children, ranging from one to six. The children in the study ranged in age from 1 to 5.

Eleven mothers acknowledged caregiver-to-caregiver violence in their early memories. Eight of them mentioned how devastated they were as children due to domestic violence. On top of that, five respondents stated family members mistreated them physically or sexually as youngsters, and one said they were ignored. Seven of their caregivers said they drank or used drugs.

Results

Childcare in Context

Nature, incidence, brutality, and measurement of Domestic violence is described as abuse in personal relationships. A total of 15 moms described physical abuse including slapping, pushing,

kicking, punching and strangling. Five mothers mentioned sex violence. Eight moms defined personal liberty interference as purposeful limits on daily activities like job or family visits, financial restrictions, and incarceration. Anger, threats, and mockery were identified as psychological abuse by 15 moms. Many types of abuse coexisted. Sixty-four percent of moms reported both mental and physical abuse.

Conclusion

Domestic violence and parenting were discussed from the perspective of maltreated women in this training. All of the moms in this study had experienced domestic violence, which they apparent as destructive to their children. Mothers blamed domestic violence for changes in their children's family dynamics, such as the death of their father and placement in foster care.

